

A Suggested Program For Teaching Social Life Skills And Its Effect On Developing Psychological Rigidity And Affirmative Behavior Skills Among Prince Sattam Bin Abdul-Aziz University Students

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 19, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: February 19, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords: Social Skills, Psychological Rigidity, Skills Of Affirmative Behavior</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4551124</p>	<p><i>This study aimed to identify the level of Social life skills and its impact on the development of psychological rigidity and the skills of affirmative behavior among students of prince Sattam bin Abdul-Aziz university Furthermore. The study sample consists of (36) students of fifth and sixth at education college, who they were randomly distributed equally into experimental and control groups; each group consists (18) students. Researcher used the following instruments in data collection: Social skills scale, skills of affirmative behavior and A proposed program to teach Social life skills and its impact on the development of psychological rigidity. According to the study results, the researcher found statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the average of the sample (experimental and controls) on the post-measurement of all social life skills, and differences were in favor of experimental group in all skills. Besides, there were statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the average of the sample (experimental and controls) on the post-measurement of mental rigidity, and differences were for the experimental group who all have psychological rigidity. Also, there were statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the average of the sample (experimental and controls) on the post-measurement of skills of affirmative behavior and differences were for the experimental group who all have skills of affirmative behavior, which indicating to the effectiveness of Education program and its role in improving Social life skills and modifying the psychological rigidity and the skills of affirmative behavior among the study sample.</i></p>

Introduction

A person is of a social nature, and his tireless search for the fulfillment of himself and his entity needs a set of social skills that facilitate his process of communicating and interacting with his neighborhood and help him fulfill his aspirations and hopes. As a result of this importance, Social and Emotional Education Foundation members developed various basic skills for social and emotional skills. They are effective communication, the ability to collaborate with others, emotional self-control and appropriate expression, taking a psychological perspective, optimism, humor, and self-awareness include strength, the ability to plan and set goals, solve problems and resolve conflicts logically (Elias & Weissberg, 2000).

Besides the social skills that students gain from the surrounding societal environment, it also increases the emotional skills that are among the essential elements in the interaction between a person and his environment, and responses occur in response to an essential change in the environment, where emotions strongly influence the behavior of students within the surrounding community, his understanding of others, his understanding of the surrounding environment, his participation in various activities and the development of his social behavior enables him to control his emotions and the appropriate expression about them, which affects his personality as a whole (Abu Hammad, 2016).

Therefore, any early deficiency in these skills may lead to a negative effect that accrues in the human personality and on education at its various stages later on, as the low social skills of students negatively affect their self-esteem, personal satisfaction and development, and positive attitudes towards learning, teachers must take an active role in helping students acquire, develop and refine the social and emotional skills necessary for important social relationships and interactions (Morris, 2002).

From the above, it can be said that social skills are imperative for all individuals in any society. As it is one of the basic requirements that an individual needs to be compatible with himself and with the community in which he lives and to live with him, as it enables him to interact smart with society, and help him to face daily problems and interact with life situations.

The study problem and its questions

The problem of the low level of psychological stiffness and the loss of assertive identity among university students increases especially in the first university stages, due to the feeling of their inability to express their feelings, their emotions, or what is on their minds, which results in fear and anxiety towards their professional and social future. In the context of all of this, the student may withdraw from social participation because of what this low level of personality imposes on him. Accordingly, he seems unable to deal with the life situations that confront him with a high level of social and emotional skills, and endures crises and pressures and self-assertion. In light of the above, the study problem can be formulated in the following questions:

1. Are there statistically significant differences at the level of statistical significance ($0.05 \geq \alpha$) between the averages of the study sample individuals (experimental group, control group) on the scale of their social life skills attributable to the training program?
2. Are there statistically significant differences at the level of statistical significance ($0.05 \geq \alpha$) between the averages of the study sample individuals (experimental group, control group) on their psychometric scale attributable to the proposed training program?
3. Are there statistically significant differences at the level of statistical significance ($0.05 \geq \alpha$) between the mean estimates of the individuals of the study sample (the experimental group and the control group) on the scale of the skills they have attributed to the proposed training program?

Study hypotheses

1. There are statistically significant differences, at the level of statistical significance ($0.05 \geq \alpha$) between the averages of the study sample individuals (experimental group, control group) on the scale of their social life skills attributable to the training program?
2. There are statistically significant differences, at the level of statistical significance ($0.05 \geq \alpha$) between the averages of the study sample individuals (experimental group, control group) on the scale of their psychological rigidity attributable to the proposed training program?
3. There are statistically significant differences, at the level of statistical significance ($0.05 \geq \alpha$) between the averages of the study sample individuals (experimental group, control group) on the scale of affirmative behavior skills attributed to the proposed training program?

Study Objectives

The present study aims to

- 1- Preparing a program to teach social life skills and its effect on developing psychological rigidity and affirmative behavior skills among students of Prince Sattam bin Abdulaziz University.
- 2- Preparing a scale for developing psychological rigidity appropriate for university students.
- 3- Setting an affirmative behavior skills scale that fits the study sample.

The Importance of the Study

The importance of this study is evident in two ways

Theoretical importance:

The study's importance lies in the fact that it deals with one of the most important aspects of the individual's personality, namely psychological rigidity and affirmative behavior. Likewise, the novelty of the variables derived from positive psychology, which is a necessity to take care of to evaluate its effectiveness, shed light on the problem of the low level of psychological rigidity and affirmative behavior among the youth. The importance of the study also lies in preparing a program to teach social life skills and its effect on developing psychological rigidity and affirmative behavior skills among students of Prince Sattam bin Abdulaziz University.

Applied importance

The practical importance of the current study lies in that it is useful in shedding more light on developing psychological rigidity and the skills of affirmative behavior in the undergraduate youth category, and it is expected that the results of the study will produce results that assist decision-makers by introducing skills, activities, and training that develop psychological rigidity and affirmative behavior skills in decisions, plans, and curricula, and the preparation of advisory, training and educational programs that include activities and services that help in developing the capabilities of students and refine their personalities.

Terminology of study

Educational programs: A plan or method that includes a set of guiding methods and procedures for which (18) students have been trained through training sessions. The program consists of (30) sessions, which were implemented over (13) weeks. The group training program is procedurally defined in this research as: a set of social skills that take place through a set of activities and exercises, appropriate to Prince Sattam bin Abdulaziz University students' characteristics, with the aim of training them to develop these skills.

Social life skills: They are behavioral patterns and activities that increase the process of social interaction with others through various social relationships and in acceptable ways so that a human learns the social and emotional dealings that enable him to communicate and effectively interact with others, and to avoid unacceptable responses. It consists of a set of social skills, such as the skills of forming relationships and positive communication with others, and self-control skills, self-awareness skills through real awareness of them and the events around them, decision-making skills, problem-solving skills, skills of cooperation and empathy with others, and skills of assuming self-responsibility (personal), self-assertion skills, self-esteem skills, and art of thinking skills (Parks, 1985). Social skills are defined procedurally in this research. As the degree obtained by the student through the social skills scale.

Psychological Hardiness: It is a general belief of an individual in his efficacy and his ability to use all the mental and social resources available to him to effectively perceive, explain, and confront stressful life events (Kaur, J & Singh, K, 2009) As the researcher defines it procedurally: the degree obtained by the examiner in the measure of psychological rigidity prepared for this purpose.

Affirmative behavior: The individual's ability to adequately express "rhetoric and behavior" about his feelings, thoughts, and opinions towards the people and attitudes around him and claim his "deserved" rights without injustice or aggression (Taha, 2000). As the researcher defines it procedurally: The score that the examiner gets on the affirmative behavior skills scale designed for this purpose.

Study limits:

The following determinants determine the current study:

- Objective limits: The research is limited to a proposed program for teaching social life skills and its effect on developing psychological rigidity and affirmative behavior skills among students of Prince Sattam bin Abdulaziz University
- Human limits: Students of the College of Education at Prince Sattam bin Abdulaziz University
- Spatial limits: it is limited to Prince Sattam bin Abdulaziz University in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.
- Time limits: Study tools were applied in the academic year 2018-2019.

Theoretical framework

The theoretical framework consists of the following concepts:

First: social skills

Several definitions of social skills were received for a group of scholars, and these definitions came close to the content. Where (Lee, 1977) mentioned that social skills are "a dynamic procedure that includes the individual's cognitive, linguistic, and social capabilities, and developing these capabilities so that they become effective strategies in different environments" (Ibrahim, 2012). (Riggio, 1990) defines social skills as: "the individual's ability to reactively and socially expressively, in addition to his skill in controlling and organizing his non-verbal expressions, such as his ability to control emotion, and to receive and interpret the emotions of others, and his ability to play the role and self-evocation socially." The researcher defines social skills as: models and rules of learned behaviors through which the individual can interact and influence positively on others in specific situations, which leads to personal and social harmony and a feeling of mental health and raise the level of quality of life.

The importance of social skills

Social skills occupy a great importance in human life, due to their necessity in building and managing social relations and managing labor relations effectively. Through it - for example - the leader can change effectively, build and lead the work team, and the ability to persuade, and then the availability of those skills and the effectiveness of their use by leaders enables them to influence others and raise their levels of performance, and thus achieving the goals of the organization in which they work. It is also extremely important in training programs for all groups with special needs; the social problems that this group faces are due to many reasons, the most important of which is the lack of social skills. It also enables the individual to control different forms of his behavior and increase his ability to deal with irrational behavior issued by others, and it enables him to establish and maintain a close relationship with those around him (Abu Mualla, 2006; Al-Helou, 2008).

The negative aspects of weak social skills

There are many negative aspects related to the weak social skills of the learner, including (Al-Harbi, 2003; Sharqi, 2003):

1. Involvement in many of the problems of interaction with colleagues and management in a way that reduces the possibility of overcoming differences in personal relationships, and escalating them - sometimes - in a way that may lead to violent conflicts, as a result of the weak social skills needed in the interaction, especially the skills of social sensing and communication, emotional understanding and self-control.
2. Adopting unrealistic expectations, and perhaps adopting some ineffective ideas, Which results in a belief in its authenticity, and behavior in a non-functional or effective manner, which exacerbates problems, provokes conflicts and wastes energy in institutions.

3. Weak social skills are sometimes associated with depression, as it is difficult for low social skills to express their feelings. Being informed about their concerns, and the suffering they feel for others, and instead, they tend to self-perpetuate, which amplifies its negative effects on the psychological and physical levels, which leads to the appearance of some depressive, moody and psychological symptoms.

Second: psychological rigidity

Kobasa (1979) defines it as: a set of personality traits that act as a source or cradle for difficult life events, and it represents a general belief or trend of the individual in his ability to exploit all of his resources, psychological capabilities, and the available environment; to realize the difficult events of life without distorting them, to explain them logically and objectively, and to live with them positively. It includes three main dimensions: commitment, control, and challenge. (kaur, J & Singh, K, 2009) defined it as: a general characteristic of the personality, as diverse environmental experiences create and develop the individual since childhood. (Angel, 2008) defines it as: it is actions on the part of the individual that evaluate and face stressful events, which can affect his health, so the components of rigidity can prepare the individual to evaluate the stressful events by making them less threatening, to be able to view himself as more efficient in dealing with it, and to rely on strategies that focus on the problem and seek support, to rely less on strategies to focus on feelings and distance from confrontation. Brooks (2005) defined it as the ability of an individual to deal effectively with stress, and the ability to adapt to daily challenges and difficulties, and deal with frustration, mistakes, trauma and daily problems to develop specific and realistic goals, to solve problems and to interact seamlessly with others. And respect them and self-esteem.

The importance of psychological rigidity

Psychological rigidity acts as a psychological variable, mitigating the impact of stressful events on an individual's physical and mental health; whereas, more solid people are subject to stress, not to get sick, and are more able to benefit from methods of coping with stress; to benefit them in reducing the threat of stressful events by seeing them from a broad perspective, analyzing them to their sub-components and developing appropriate solutions for them. And it affects the assessment of the individual's cognitive of the stressful event itself and the consequent threat to security, mental health, and self-esteem, it also affects the individual's evaluation of coping methods, which are the ways in which the individual experiences the stressful event (facing problems - escaping - taking responsibility - seeking support - self-control). And researchers argue that even if individuals with a high degree of psychological rigidity. By estimating the stresses that they constitute pressure for them, however, the characteristics of their personality continue to act as a shield from the impact of the pressures by facilitating the choice of consensual confrontational methods, or by ceasing non-consensual behavior, as individuals with the highest rigidity theoretically tend to use the transformational confrontational method, in it, they change events that can generate pressure into growth opportunities, and as a result, we find them compatible with stressful events in an optimistic and effective way. On the contrary, individuals with low stiffness rely on retrograde confrontation, in which they avoid or move away from situations that can generate pressure (Radi, 2008).

Dimensions of psychological rigidity

Psychological rigidity includes three dimensions:

- 1- Commitment: This means the strong commitment of an individual to different life situations, active participation and integration in social relations and ongoing activities. It is a type of psychological contracting that an individual adheres to towards himself, his goals, values, and others around him (Cotton, 1990).
- 2- Control or settings: This means the internal convictions of the human being; that is, the human experience that he has a specific or clear impact on the events of his life. It indicates the belief that people who have the ability to play an active and effective role, have responsibility for their lives and take personal responsibility for what happens to them (kaur, J & Singh, K, 2009).
- 3- The challenge: That is, the individual considers the requirements of life and its fatigue as challenges and not threats, and leads to motives to act and motives for adjustment, and that what changes in the aspects of his life is more exciting and necessary for growth than a threat to him; this helps him to initiate and explore the environment and knowledge of psychological and social resources that help him to face pressure effectively. The challenge is the tendency to view the unexpected change or potential threat as a positive challenge, rather than a threatening and detestable event (Angel, 2008).

Third: Affirmative behavior

The term affirmative behavior appeared by Salter, since Pavlov formulated his theory of classical conditioning, many researchers have employed the principles of this theory in psychological service, among these researchers (Salter), who distinguished between two types of excitatory behavior versus retractive behavior, Salter explained

that the child is born with an exclusive personality that responds to the stimuli of the environment, as he behaves without restrictions, which leads to the development of the excitatory pattern in his personality if we do not stop this behavior, where these and other negative behaviors are ceased with the positive parenting treatment that children have been brought up from a young age (Taha, 2000). Then came Lazarus, who was among the researchers who authenticated the affirmation, where he demonstrated that affirmative behavior consists of four responses: the individual's ability to say no, the ability to do requirements, the ability to express positive and negative feelings, and the ability to start, continue and end conversations. Then Wolpe came after him, in the term assertiveness, which means the individual obtaining his full rights and freedom of emotional expression without fear and without prejudice to the rights of others, then, in 1973, he modified this view of assertiveness in order to conform to the requirements of leveling, so he defined it again as the ability of the individual to express his emotions, as it happens in different situations and with ordinary people, this expression appears as a socially acceptable behavior. Through the foregoing, the scientific foundations of affirmative behavior emerged at the hands of Salter, with excitatory behavior and regressive behavior. And by applying the principles of classical conditioning for the researcher (Pavlov) to come after him (Wolpe) to be the first founder of confirmation, this is because excitatory behavior includes a kind of aggression, and thus the concept of self-assertion has become more specific (Wolpe, 1979), Abdel-Sattar (2001) defines that affirmation is one aspect of personality that shows its association with success or failure in social relationships. It includes expressing oneself and defending personal rights when they penetrate. Ati (2004) defines self-affirmation as the individual's ability to positively conduct differently, whether in feelings, thoughts, or behaviors. And through which the individual can obtain his rights and achieve his goals. While Raccuse defined it as: "Qualitative-situational behavior, learned from seven partial independent categories They are: acknowledging personal shortcomings, offering congratulations or compliments, rejecting unreasonable demands, starting and continuing with social interactions, expressing positive emotions, expressing different opinions about others, and asking the other to change some of his undesirable behaviors (Farhan, 2011).

The main characteristics of affirmative behavior

There are basic features and characteristics of affirmative behavior, the most important of which are: (Kokkinos & Panayiotou, 2004); (Bickford, et. Al. 2009).

1. Qualitative: It includes a number of qualitative skills, and that regardless of the difference in the specific categories of this behavior, there are common elements that can be drawn from them, they are: First: the ability to express positive and negative feelings, and opinions that are in agreement with others, or that are different from them. Second: Defend private rights and insist on exercising them. Third: Initiating social interaction. Fourth: Rejection of unreasonable demands.
2. Does not involve violating the rights of others: Researchers were keen to take into account the social dimension when determining the nature of affirmative behavior in order to provide a more realistic definition of this behavior, for example, "Lang and Jaco Bosque" define assertion as "defending private rights, expressing thoughts, feelings, and beliefs in an explicit and direct manner, and in appropriate ways that do not violate the rights of others."
3. Its effectiveness is relative: that is, confirmation is not always effective. Affirmative behavior may bring more trouble to the individual, and the extent of its effectiveness depends on a number of variables such as: the criterion used in determining effectiveness, is it the person himself or others or the objective objectives of the behavior?
4. Situation: Confirmation varies in some degree as a result of being affected by a situation in different degrees, for example, it is affected by the characteristics of the other party in the interaction situation, and the characteristics of the situation with what it contains from other people whether they are friends, relatives, or strangers as well as the physical characteristics, and the characteristics of the surrounding cultural context, and the extent of urging or desisting of affirmative.
5. Learnable: Affirmative behavior is acquired and it is learnable, whether in a systematic way, such as participation in affirmative training programs, which means developing his sub-skills, or in a subjective way, as he rises through the experience and social education that the individual acquires throughout his history, as well as his attempts to experience experiences that help him to improve his level of assertion.
6. Includes verbal and non-verbal elements: Emphasis may be issued as a way to express an individual's feelings and opinions in the form of a verbal response Such as: I do not agree with what you say, or non-verbal, such as placing the right index finger in a position perpendicular to the mouth to warn who is speaking with you inappropriately, and confirmed behavior is the result of each of its components (verbal and non-verbal).

Previous studies

First: Previous studies dealing with psychological rigidity

Al-Ganzouri (2017) conducted a study aimed at the effectiveness of a counseling program to develop the psychological rigidity of mothers, and its effect on the quality of life of their children with mobility disabilities among primary school students. The study sample consisted of (30) mothers with mobility disabilities in the vocational rehabilitation centers in Al-Jala'a, Al-Abbasi, and Talkha. Their ages range between (25-49) who have a low degree of psychological rigidity, and to achieve the goals of the study, the researcher used a measure of psychological rigidity for mothers with physical disabilities, a measure of the quality of life for children with disabilities, A mentorship program to develop the psychological rigidity of mothers of physically disabled children. The results of the study showed that there are statistically significant differences between the mean levels of the degrees of the experimental and control groups of the mothers of the physically disabled children in the dimensional measurement on the scale of psychological rigidity (dimensions and the total degree) after applying the counseling program in favor of the experimental group. And there are statistically significant differences between the mean scores for the experimental group scores of mothers of Physically disabled children in the pre and post measurements. On the psychological rigidity scale (dimensions and total score) before and after applying the counseling program in favor of post-measurement. And there were no statistically significant differences between the mean scores of the experimental group scores of mothers of Physically disabled children. in the dimensional and consecutive scales on the scale of psychological rigidity (dimensions and total score).

Mustafa (2017) conducted a study aimed at verifying the effectiveness of a counseling program in developing psychological resilience among a sample of mothers of mentally retarded children, the study sample consisted of (20) mothers of mothers of mentally retarded children, whose ages ranged between (25-45) years. And to achieve the goals of the study, the researcher used the psychological resilience measure for mothers of mentally disabled children, and the Stanford Binet scale, the fifth image. And the measure of the socio-economic and cultural level. The results of the study showed the effectiveness of the counseling program in improving the psychological resilience of mothers of mentally retarded children.

Al-Manahi (2015) conducted a study aimed at designing a counseling program to develop psychological resilience for depressed people in light of CBT theory, and the detection of the impact of this in reducing the severity of depression, and checking the continuity of the effectiveness of the counseling program after two months of its application. And the study sample consisted of (16) university students, and their ages ranged between (19-23) years. To achieve the goals of the study, the researcher used a measure of psychological rigidity and depression (before / after) on both groups. The pilot program was applied to the pilot group only. The results of the study showed that there were differences in the mean scores of the experimental group in the measures of psychological rigidity and depression in favor of post-measurement, as well as in the measure of psychological rigidity and depression between the experimental group and the control group in the dimensional measurement in favor of the experimental group. The study also revealed that there were no statistically significant differences in the mean scores of the experimental group in psychological rigidity between dimensional and consecutive measurement.

Second: Previous studies dealing with affirmative behavior skills

(Parisa & Bayat, 2010) conducted a study aimed at knowing the impact of training on social skills in increasing assertiveness and self-esteem on a sample of (20) students, their ages ranged between (9-11) years, and the sample was chosen based on the low female students' scores on the affirmative behavior scale. To achieve the goals of the study, the researchers used the Richi & Gambrill (1975) scale for self-expression, and a social skills training program developed by them, the results of the study showed that there are statistically significant differences between the arithmetic mean for the estimates of the study sample individuals for the degree of affirmative behavior and for the benefit of the members of the experimental group.

Abu Hammad (2014) conducted a study aimed at revealing the effectiveness of a counseling program based on cognitive behavioral theory in raising the level of behavior assertion among students of Salman bin Abdulaziz University, the sample of the study consisted of (120) students from the College of Education students, divided into two groups: control and experimental. To achieve the goals of the study, the researcher used two tools for the study, the first: a measure of affirmative behavior, and the second: a pilot program to raise the level of assertive behavior. The results of the study showed that there are statistically significant differences between the arithmetic mean for the study sample estimates of the degree of affirmative behavior they have (as a whole) for the post-response attributed to a variable interaction [treatment (training program, without training program), and academic level (first, second, third, fourth)].

The Meqdad (2015) study aimed to build a counseling program to reinforce affirmative behavior among primary school students in the city of Bahrain. The sample consisted of (14) primary school students (sixth grade), whose ages ranged between (11-12) years. To achieve the goals of the study, the researcher used a affirmative behavior scale and an indicative program. The results of the study showed that there were statistically significant differences between the arithmetic mean for the estimates of the study sample individuals on the affirmative behavior scale and in favor of the experimental group measurement. And it was randomly divided using paper

scraps into two equal groups: experimental and controlling. The first one was exposed to the activities of the instructional program, while the other did not receive any instructional sessions.

Bashir (2016) conducted a study aimed at revealing the effectiveness of an integrated, selective counseling program for developing affirmative behavior. And verify the impact of this program on increasing both self-efficacy, social competence, and academic performance. The study sample consisted of (60) students, and to achieve the goals of the study, the researcher used a measure of affirmative behavior, a measure of self-efficacy, a measure of social competence, Integrated selective mentoring program. The results of the study showed the effectiveness of the program used in developing affirmative behavior, and the presence of a positive effect of this in increasing self-efficacy and social efficiency among members of the experimental group.

General comment on previous studies:

It is clear from the previous literature that the subject of the current study and its sample are among the topics that did not receive attention and research by specialists in psychology; where the researcher did not find a study similar to the current study in terms of its study a proposed program for teaching social life skills and its effect on developing psychological rigidity and affirmative behavior skills among students of Prince Sattam bin Abdulaziz University, and that is within the limits of the researcher's knowledge within the framework of the Arab and foreign studies available to him. This reinforces the research significance of the current study. The results of the current study agreed with most of the previous studies on the effect of educational or training programs on developing psychological rigidity and affirmative behavior skills on the experimental study sample. The researcher also benefited from previous studies in preparing the measures used in the study, and in formulating its goals and interpreting its results.

Study Approach:

The current study relies on the semi-experimental curriculum, as it is based on ensuring the effectiveness of a proposed program for teaching social life skills and its impact on developing psychological rigidity and affirmative behavior skills for students of Prince Sattam bin Abdulaziz University.

Statistical treatments:

The researcher used the following statistical treatments: arithmetic averages and standard deviations, multiple accompanying variance analysis, Pearson correlation coefficients, and Alpha Krumbach equation.

Study procedures:

In preparing the current study, the researcher relied on a set of steps that were implemented through successive phases of time, according to the following:

1. Review the literature and previous studies related to the study and formulate the theoretical framework for the study.
2. Drafting study hypotheses in the light of the theoretical framework and the results of previous studies.
3. Preparation and codification of study tools which included: a measure of social life skills, psychological rigidity, affirmative behavior skills, and educational program.
4. Choosing a semi-experimental design appropriate for the study, and Choosing the sample and distribute it to the two study groups: (experimental and control).
5. Field study procedures, which included: First: legalizing study tools to verify their validity and reliability, and thus the validity of use. Second: Applying the scale (pre-test), after reading and clarifying it, and creating the appropriate atmosphere for application to the two study groups: (control and experimental) to ensure that the two groups are equal before applying the training program. Third: Implementing the training program in (30) sessions, by two sessions per week, in addition to the introductory session and the closing session, and the session duration was (40) minutes. And after creating the appropriate atmosphere for the application. Fourth: Applying the scale (post-test), after reading and clarifying it, and creating the appropriate atmosphere for application to the two study groups: (control and experimental).
6. Interpret the study results in light of the theoretical framework and previous studies, and provide a number of recommendations.

The study sample

The sample of the study consisted of (36) students, from Prince Sattam bin Abdulaziz University students, at the undergraduate level, from the fifth and sixth levels, whose ages ranged between (19-21) years. The final study sample was chosen based on their obtaining the lowest scores on the scale of social life skills, Psychological rigidity, and affirmative behavior skills.

They were divided into two equal groups, one is experimental, and the other is a control group, each consisting of (18) students.

Study tools

The first tool: the measure of social life skills:

The researcher reviewed educational literature and previous studies that were concerned with measuring social life skills, including: The Helweh Study (2008) and Abu Mualla Study (2006), and because it does not fit the

nature of the study members, the researcher decided to design a scale that suits the age group of the study sample. Therefore, the researcher designed a scale of (90) items. The answer for each paragraph is graded by choosing one of the three alternatives (always: 2 degrees), (sometimes: zero), (never: one degree). The overall score for the scale ranged between (0-180). To check the validity of the scale for use: This step aims to: Verification of the stability of the scale: the Alpha Cronbach method was used, and the method of reapplying the test, ranged between (0.6 - 0.8). With the method of reapplying the test, the values of the stability coefficients ranged between (0.7-0.9). The validity of the scale was verified: according to two methods, they are: First: Presenting the scale to a group of specialized arbitrators to obtain the largest number of suggestions on the validity of the vocabulary. The result of the arbitration indicated the amendment of some paragraphs, and the amendment of the language formulation in proportion to the sample of the study. And the calculation of agreement rates between the arbitrators amounted to (80%), which is an acceptable rate. Second: Calculating the consistency of the scale by calculating the correlation coefficient between the degree of each individual and the degree of the axis to which the item belongs, then calculating the correlation coefficient between the degree of the axis and the total degree of the scale, and calculate the internal consistency of the scale by: Calculation of correlation coefficients between the score of each individual and the total degree of the axis to which the item belongs, and calculating the correlation coefficient between the scores of the axes of the social skills scale and the total degree: all of which are a function of (0.01).

The second tool: Psychometric Rigidity Scale:

After referring to scientific sources, and some previous studies, including the study of Manahi (2015), and the study of Radi (2008), the psychometric scale included areas: commitment, challenge, control, patience, and responsibility. And the overall scale consists of (30) phrases, and the answer to the phrases falls in four levels, which are: (Fully applies - often applies - sometimes applies - never applies to me). The grades for each phrase range from four degrees to one degree, so the answer is given (exactly applies) four degrees, while the answer (never applies to me) is given one degree. The researcher has presented the measure of psychological rigidity under study to a group of professors specialized in the field of psychology and counseling to judge its validity and the relevance of its phrases. They explained that the scale statements are comprehensive in the areas of Psychometric Scale. And the researcher has verified the stability and validity of the scale on the reconnaissance sample, consisting of (23) individuals. Reliability was calculated by the alpha-stability factor. The coefficients for the total degree of psychological rigidity were (0.86) and Spearman Brown (0.88), It is of high stability, which makes it reassuring to use the scale on the study sample. The researcher also calculated the validity of the scale by the internal homogeneity of the study tool by calculating correlation coefficients between the degree of each phrase and the total degree of phrases, and all statements were indicative at the level (0.01) of each phrase in degree, where the association of phrases with the overall degree of the scale ranged between (0.75-0.80), which is a high validity that confirms the affiliation of all phrases with the measure of psychological rigidity.

The third tool: Affirmative Behavior Skills Scale:

The researcher used the Rathous 1973 confirmation behavior scale after making appropriate adjustments to the scale to suit the study sample. Where the scale is in its final form of (30) items. To ensure the validity of the study tool, it was presented to a group of arbitrators specialized in psychology, psychological counseling and sociology; in order to express their views on the wording of the phrases, and get rid of ambiguity, similarity, overlap and repetition between phrases, the extent of their suitability for individuals to whom the scale will be applied, and the validity, accuracy, clarity and ease of the paragraphs, the degree of affiliation for each paragraph of the domain in which it was mentioned in the scale. The researcher adopted the opinion of the arbitrators on what percentage (55-70%) to change the paragraph and delete it or add new paragraphs, and in the light of the previous arbitrators' opinions, the paragraphs were deleted, others were modified, and the study tool consisted of (30) items out of (35) paragraphs. It is suitable for the sample to which the study will be applied and they are students of Prince Sattam bin Abdulaziz University. Indicators of the stability of the scale were identified. By using the Pearson correlation coefficient, to calculate the Test-Retest stability factor. Correlation coefficient values for the scale ranged from (0.87). The internal consistency coefficient of Alpha Cronpach was calculated, as the values of correlation coefficients ranged from (0.93).

Fourth Tool: Educational programs:

The researcher prepared the program according to the following steps:

- The main objective of the program: with a view to developing psychological rigidity and affirmative behavior skills among students of Prince Sattam bin Abdulaziz University.
- The general principles of the program: The application of the program was subject to a set of rules, which were adhered to by the researcher and students, including: confidentiality of information exchanged during training, adherence to the schedule of sessions, development of student capabilities in the social, emotional, and spiritual aspects, and adherence to the homework system.
- Spatial limits of the program: The sessions of the program are implemented in the College of Education at Prince Sattam bin Abdulaziz University.

- The target group of the program: The program is applied to a sample of (18) students (the experimental group) from Prince Sattam bin Abdulaziz University students.]
- Duration of the program and the number of its sessions: A proposed program for teaching social life skills and its effect on developing psychological rigidity and affirmative behavior among Prince Sattam bin Abdulaziz University students was composed of (30) training sessions; as the experimental group underwent the tutorial, as for the control group, it did not receive any training on the program, and it took 13 weeks to implement the program.
- Means used during the application of the program: the blackboard to display instructions and clarify ambiguities, the presentations device for use in the slideshow for the trainees, and homework papers assigned to students.
- Resources for preparing the program: The researcher built his educational program based on his observations and conclusions during the preparation and application of the study tool, and on the theoretical framework of the study and previous Arab and foreign studies, as well as studies that dealt with building an educational or training program to develop psychological rigidity and affirmative behavior skills.
- Defining the program dimensions: The program was prepared according to the following: skills of forming relationships and positive communication with others, and skills of self-control, and the skills of self-awareness through its real awareness of it and the events around it, decision-making skills, problem-solving skills, skills of cooperation and empathy with others, skills of assuming self-responsibility (personal), skills of self-affirmation, skills of self-esteem, and art of thinking skills.
- Program validity: After completing the preparation of the educational program, the researcher presented it to a number of arbitrators (professors and specialists) at Prince Sattam bin Abdulaziz University, and King Saud University to judge the sincerity of the program in terms of its appropriateness to the specific specifications of each field, and the link of the program with the measured features, and the researcher reviewed the opinions of the arbitrators, and what was agreed upon was taken at (80%) or more.
- Program evaluation: It was based on two types of evaluation, namely: the structural evaluation: where the researcher evaluated each session of the program by asking participants about their opinion, through the evaluation cards, and provide feedback on what happened during each session.
- Final evaluation: where the researcher applied the social skills questionnaire and the point of control at the end of the last session of the educational program sessions and it was statistically processed to ensure that the program achieved its goals.

The results of the study and its discussion:

The first hypothesis states that: There are statistically significant differences, at the level of statistical significance ($0.05 \geq \alpha$) between the averages of the study sample individuals (experimental group, control group) on the scale of their social life skills attributable to the training program?

To answer the first question related to the presence of statistically significant differences between the averages of the study sample individuals (experimental group, control group) on the scale of their social life skills, attributable to the proposed training program, the arithmetic mean, standard deviations, and T-Test For Independent Samples were found, and Table 1 illustrates this.

Table (1): Arithmetic circles, standard deviations, and (T) testing of independent samples between the mean scores of the experimental group and the control group on the post-social life skills scale

Skill	Group	Number	Arithmetic average	T Value	Degrees of freedom	Statistical significance
Skills of forming relationships and positive communication with others	Control group	18	0.75	- 3.555-	34	0.001
	Experimental group	18	1.13	- 3.555-	34	0.002
Self-control skills	Control group	18	0.65	- 5.084-	34	0.000
	Experimental group	18	1.18	- 5.084-	34	0.000
Self-awareness skills	Control group	18	0.83	- 3.571-	34	0.001
	Experimental group	18	1.17	- 3.571-	34	0.001
Decision making skills	Control group	18	0.68	- 5.522-	34	0.000

	Experimental group	18	1.14	- 5.522-	34	0.000
Problem solving skills	Control group	18	0.49	- 5.771-	34	0.000
	Experimental group	18	1.21	- 5.771-	34	0.000
Skills of cooperation and empathy with others	Control group	18	0.74	- 4.985-	34	0.000
	Experimental group	18	1.09	- 4.985-	34	0.000
Self-responsibility skills (Personal)	Control group	18	0.89	- 2.768-	34	0.009
	Experimental group	18	1.05	- 2.768-	34	0.009
Self-assertion skills	Control group	18	1.21	- 2.725-	34	0.010
	Experimental group	18	1.38	- 2.725-	34	0.010
Self-esteem skills	Control group	18	0.85	- 2.524-	34	0.016
	Experimental group	18	1.06	- 2.524-	34	0.017
Social Life Skills Scale	Control group	18	0.75	- 5.179-	34	0.000
	Experimental group	18	1.12	- 5.179-	34	0.000

Table (1) shows that there are statistically significant differences between the mean of the control group and the experimental group attributable to the proposed training program on the scale of social life skills (post) and in favor of the experimental group. And it is clear from Table (1) that there are statistically significant differences between the mean of the control group and the experimental group due to the proposed training program on all skills of social life skills scale (Skills of forming relationships and positive communication with others, self-control skills, self-awareness skills, Decision-making skills, problem-solving skills, skills of cooperation and empathy with others, skills of assuming personal self-responsibility, self-assertion skills, self-esteem skills) and for the benefit of the experimental group. The results of the first hypothesis revealed the presence of statistically significant differences at the significance level ($0.05 \geq \alpha$) in the responses of the members of the experimental group on the study tool (the measure of social life skills) in favor of the responses of the members of the experimental group on the post-measurement, and this means developing and improving the social skills of the group that received training in the training program (the experimental group).

In comparison with the group that did not receive training in the training program (control group). Thus, these results are consistent with the results of the studies of: Al-Janzouri (2017) and Mustafa's study (2017). Where the researcher attributes the success of the program to the method of teaching the program, and the methodological activities it includes for the members of the experimental group, which in turn helped them to acquire social life skills, and the use of educational activities that encourage them to think, and stimulate the largest number of senses, and rely mostly on direct experiences, and self-learning, as it depends on the use of open-ended questions that lead to an increase in the ability to generate many diverse ideas; which increases the student's confidence in his abilities and positive appreciation of himself.

The second hypothesis states that: There are statistically significant differences, at the level of statistical significance ($0.05 \geq \alpha$) between the averages of the estimates of the members of the study sample (experimental group, control group) on the scale of their psychological rigidity attributable to the proposed training program?

To answer the first question related to the presence of statistically significant differences among the averages of the estimates of the individuals of the study sample (experimental group, control group) on their psychological rigidity scale attributable to the proposed training program, mathematical circles, standard deviations and T-Test for Independent Samples were found and Table 2 illustrates this.

Table 2: Arithmetic averages, standard deviations and (T) testing of independent samples between the two mean scores (experimental group, control group) on the scale of their psychological rigidity attributable to the proposed training program

Skill	Group type	Number	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	T value	Degrees of freedom	Statistical significance
Patience	Control group	18	1.315	0.213	-	34	0.00
	Experimental group	18	2.852	0.261	19.343-		
Challenge	Control group	18	1.546	0.254	-	34	0.00
	Experimental group	18	2.843	0.414	11.316-		
control	Control group	18	1.259	0.208	-	34	0.00
	Experimental group	18	2.639	0.349	14.412-		
Commitment	Control group	18	2.296	0.364	-	34	0.00
	Experimental group	18	4.963	0.452	19.490-		
Responsibility	Control group	18	0.982	0.180	-	34	0.00
	Experimental group	18	2.500	0.303	18.309-		
Psychological rigidity scale	Control group	18	1.264	0.182	-	34	0.00
	Experimental group	18	2.753	0.137	27.749-		

Table (2) shows that there are statistically significant differences between the mean of the control group and the experimental group due to the proposed training program on the dimensional psychological rigidity scale and in favor of the experimental group. And from Table 2, it appears that there are statistically significant differences between the mean of the control group and the experimental group due to the proposed training program on all skills of the Psychometric Rigidity Scale (patience, challenge, control, commitment, responsibility) and in favor of the experimental group. The results of the second hypothesis revealed the presence of statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($0.05 \geq \alpha$) in the responses of the members of the experimental group on the study tool (the measure of psychological rigidity) in favor of the responses of the members of the experimental group on the dimensional measurement, This means raising the level of psychological rigidity of the group that received training in the training program (the experimental group) compared to the group that did not receive training in the training program (the control group). Thus, these results are consistent with the results of each study: Al-Manahi (2015).

The researcher attributes the experimental group to the superiority of the control group in developing and raising the level of psychological rigidity, that the nature of the program used includes many discussions, ideas and social skills that have contributed to the development of psychological rigidity, the program also depends on teaching activities on some effective methods in developing social interaction and raising the level of psychological rigidity among students, and providing them with different skills, which help students to self-learn through direct experience, and to reinforce positive direct and indirect experiences experienced by students inside and outside the university, finding the opportunity to express their feelings and needs, learn to communicate with others, share their thoughts and experiences, and learn about its roles and responsibilities. This led to positive self-activation among the members of the experimental group. And their superiority over the control group. The nature of the activities presented to the students is appropriate to their needs and interests, which in turn led to stimulating their motivation to perform the activities and carry out them.

The third hypothesis states that: There are statistically significant differences, at the level of statistical significance ($0.05 \geq \alpha$) among the averages estimates of the individuals of the study sample (experimental group, control group) on the scale of affirmative behavior skills attributable to the proposed training program?

To answer the first question related to the presence of statistically significant differences between the averages of the study sample individuals (experimental group, control group) on their affirmative behavior skills scale. Attributed to the proposed training program, Arithmetic mean, standard deviations, and T-Test For Independent Samples were found, and Table 3 illustrates this.

Table 3: Arithmetic averages, standard deviations, and the T-test. For independent samples between the two mean scores (the experimental group and the control group) on their affirmative behavior scale are attributed to the proposed training program

Skill	Group type	Number	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	T value	Degrees of freedom	Statistical significance
Affirmative behavior skills	Control group	18	1.272	0.15461	-31.081	34	0.000
	Experimental group	18	2.9502	0.16902			

The results of the third hypothesis revealed the presence of statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($0.05 \geq \alpha$) in the responses of the members of the experimental group on the study tool (affirmative behavior scale) in favor of the responses of the members of the experimental group on the dimensional measurement, and this means developing affirmative behavior skills in the group that received training in the training program (the experimental group) compared to the group that did not receive training in the training program (control group). These results are consistent with the results of (Parisa & Bayat, 2010) and Abu Hammad (2014). This result is attributed to the effect of the program, due to what the researcher took into account when selecting the study sample and the theoretical framework he prepared in light of the program design. The members of the experimental group were keen to attend these sessions regularly and observe the instructions given to them during the session, and commitment to attend at the agreed time, and adhere to the instructions, and carry out homework on the dates specified for them, which are an important part of the program used in the study, and the researcher's attempt to create the appropriate psychological atmosphere to implement the sessions.

Recommendations and proposals

Through the results of the study, it recommends the following:

1. Increase studies dealing with programs based on developing positive personality traits.
2. Media awareness of the need to pay attention to developing psychological rigidity and affirmative behavior skills.
3. Holding training and educational workshops to develop psychological rigidity and affirmative behavior skills among students.
4. Including educational programs within university activities with the aim of improving assertive behavior skills.

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